

Probability Wave Reflection in Quantum Bound States?

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In a number of previous notes, we suggested writing a quantum conditional probability $P(p/x)=a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$ at each x point. This follows, it seems, from a free particle conditional probability $\exp(ipx)$ which mimics the description of a photon. In other words, probability (in a smoothed out mathematical model representing actual stochastic motion) behaves similar to a photon wave. In this note, we wish to examine the interpretation of $\exp(-ipx)$ in more detail. A particle with $-p$ momentum should travel from right to left, yet this term is considered in a left-to-right scheme. We suggest that $\exp(-ipx)$ may represent reflection at each x . If $a(p)=a(-p)$, this reflection has no added phase shift, while if $a(p)=-a(-p)$ it has an added phase shift of 3.14 . In addition, a reflection picture seems to be more in keeping with the idea of a stochastic system.

Classical Statistical Mechanics

In classical statistical mechanics (with no potential), particles have the same probability to be at any position in a volume, so this probability may be described by a constant number. One may try to extend this idea to a quantum free particle except for the experimental fact of interference of such a particle when it interacts with the potential of a two slit system. Furthermore, the particle seems to track its phase in a similar manner to a photon which is described by $\exp(ikx)$. Thus, the probability of a free quantum particle is also given as $\exp(ipx)$. The modulus of 1 everywhere accounts for equal probability at any point, but cycling behaviour due to p is also included. For a bound particle, one may consider a gas of quantum free particles $\exp(ipx)$, yet there seems to be an issue of interpretation for $\exp(-ipx)$. One may describe this as representing a particle moving backwards, but what does the phase mean in such a case? Phase tracks the distance and a particle moving backwards has negative p , but moves from a high x to a low, not vice versa. In $P(p/x)=a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$, a conditional probability, one thinks in terms of right to left motion.

Reflection

In quantum mechanics, $\exp(ipx)$ represents a forward moving particle and $\exp(-ipx)$ a backward moving one, but the backward moving particle should move from high x value to low (i.e. from right to left). In a classical system, a particle usually moves to the right during a specific time interval and to the left during a different interval suggesting two directions clearly specified in time. Quantum mechanics is stochastic, we argue, with forward and backward motion happening possible directly after each other and not during clearly defined time intervals. This stochastic (erratic) motion seems to be described by a smoothed over probability scheme using $\exp(ipx)$. One may argue that if there is both forward and backward motion, one simply uses both $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ as done in previous notes. In this note, we still consider

$\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ as forward and backward motion, but examine reflection as a possible alternative view which may help explain the two cases $a(p)=a(-p)$ and $a(p)=-a(-p)$. In addition, if one considers the average:

$$KE(\text{ave at } x+dx) = \text{Sum over } p \frac{p^2}{2m} a(p) \exp[ip(x+dx)]$$

for $p>0$, moving from $x+dx$ means one has forward motion in time, but for $-p$ backward motion in time.. Finally, a picture with reflection at each x seems to capture stochastic motion a little more clearly and may be linked a little more directly to interference.

The forms $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ already appear in electromagnetic wave reflection, so an interpretation of $\exp(-ipx)$ already exists. It seems it may be a reflected probability wave, but one which is reflected at each point x . If $a(p)=a(-p)$, there is no extra phase in the reflection while if $a(p)=-a(-p)$ there is a phase of π . As a result, at each x , there exists an ensemble of forward moving probability waves $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ and a corresponding set of reflected waves $a(-p)\exp(-ipx)$. At first this may seem unusual, but we argue that a quantum system involves stochastic motion which is described on average by probability waves. These waves seem to be a mathematical abstraction, nevertheless we argue they contain key physics such as a physical periodicity $\exp(ipx)$ and certain translation information i.e. $\exp(ip(x+dx)) = \exp(ipx) \exp(i p dx)$ while for a bound state $W(x+dx) = W(x) \exp(i (1/i \ln W/dx) x)$ where $1/i \ln W/dx = \langle p \text{ at } x \rangle$.

p/-p Cancellation

A quantum free particle is represented by $\exp(ipx)$. The momentum at any point x is: $p \exp(ipx)/\exp(ipx) = p$ just as in the classical situation. For a particle in a box with infinite potential walls, the result $W(x)=A \sin(pave x)$ leads to an average momentum of: $-A i pave \cos(pave x) / \sin(pavex)$. This contains singular at points, but multiplication by spatial density $W(x)W(x)$ causes the singularity to disappear. Nevertheless, one does not have an average of 0 as one would exist for a classical particle bouncing back and forth.

It is possible to “artificially force” p and $-p$ to average to zero at x by considering a distance L to the left of x together with $\exp(ipx)$ and a distance L to the right with $\exp(-ipx)$ moving towards the left.

At x , one has: $0 = a(p) [p \exp(ipL) - p \exp(ipL)]$ (if $a(p)=a(-p)$). We use $\exp(ipL)$ for the second term because $\Delta x = -L$. This is not the case of reflection, however, which we argue for.

In other words, a curious feature of quantum bound states is that $p \exp(ipx)$ and $-p \exp(-ipx)$ do not cancel, at least for most points. For a classical statistical mechanical gas, each p at x has a corresponding $-p$ so the average momentum is 0. Such is not the case in quantum bound states. There is a purely imaginary average conditional momentum at each x given by:

$$\langle p \text{ at } x \rangle = \text{Sum over } p \quad p P(p/x) \quad ((1))$$

If one considers a specific p / $-p$ pair, there are points where these two momenta average to 0 i.e. for $a(p)=a(-p)$:

$$a(p) p \exp(ipx) + a(-p) (-p) \exp(-ipx) = a(p)2i \sin(px) \quad ((2))$$

At zeros of $\sin(px)$ the classical result that p and $-p$ average to 0 holds, but not elsewhere. In addition there is the issue of a purely imaginary average momentum, but a bound particle may be moving in a forward and backward direction in the average of ((1)) so that is perhaps not disturbing. It is interesting to consider average kinetic energy at x :

$$\langle p^2/2m \text{ at } x \rangle = \text{Sum over } p \quad p^2/2m P(p/x) \quad ((3))$$

For the same p / $-p$ pair and $a(p)=a(-p)$:

$$a(p)p^2/2m \exp(ipx) + a(-p)p^2/2m \exp(-ipx) = a(p)^2 \cos(px) \quad ((3))$$

This, like ((2)) is periodic, but the zeros are located in different places. Maximum positive or negative kinetic energy occurs when $\sin(px)=0$ i.e. p and $-p$ cancel just as in the classical situation.

Interference and Stochasticity

Utilizing the probability wave $\exp(ipx)$ leads to interference within a bound system. Many bound systems have a spatial density with humps. We have argued in previous notes, that "cancellation" of probability waves may account for stochastic features which exist, but must be removed from averages. For example, in a stochastic system a particle at rest may be accelerated backwards to a momentum of p , then accelerated forwards to a momentum of 0 and finally forwards again to a momentum of p_1 . The overall result is that the particle starts at rest and is accelerated to p_1 . Nevertheless within this process, measurements may pick out a momentum of p in the backwards direction etc. This seems to be analogous to conditional probability waves $\exp(ipx)$ which may contribute positive kinetic energy or density for some range of x for a p / $-p$ pair (i.e. $\cos(px)$) and negative elsewhere.

Another example involves a particle scattering from a spherical potential. The wavefunction (relative conditional probability sum) is:

$$W(x)=\exp(ikx) \text{ (incoming plane wave probability)} + f(\theta,\phi) \exp(ikr)/r \quad ((4))$$

In other words, one combines the incoming and scattered probability waves. $W^*(x)W(x)$ includes interference which removes some density from the incoming plane wave to account for probability existing in the scattered wave. Thus, interference removes some probability from one process and assigns it to another. In a bound state, kinetic energy due to p / $-p$ may be removed

at one x , but added at another. Probability waves $\exp(ipx)$ may be an idealization because at one instant a particle at x with momentum p may receive a momentum hit moving it to x_2 and with p_2 , then it may be knocked backwards etc. Nevertheless, the free particle result $\exp(ipx)$, which matches experiment, demonstrates that a quantum free particle “keeps track of a kind of cycling” (which leads to two slit interference for example) and this feature must be included in the stochastic picture. This is perhaps the grounds for considering different $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ probability waves and their reflected forms $a(-p)\exp(-ipx)$ which are not relevant in the free particle two slit interference experiment.

Classical statistical mechanics is similar in that one also has numerous stochastic two particle collisions, but does describe these. Rather, one considers an average momentum probability distribution $f(p)$ which for the Maxwell-Boltzmann case is $B\exp(-pp/2mT)$ and $B_1 \exp(-pp/2mT) \exp(-V(r)/T)$ for an added potential. Given that a quantum free particle has a probability of $\exp(ipx)$, one may try to form a distribution of such free particles at each x with $\exp(-ipx)$ reflected waves accounting for the idea that motion may suddenly be reversed as in a reflection which may occur at any point.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue a quantum system is stochastic yet a free particle has a conditional probability of the form $\exp(ipx)$ and the idea of cycling included must be included in the stochastic scenario. Thus, we argue for a smoothed over probability scheme using a distribution $P(p/x) = a(p)\exp(ipx)/W(x)$, but this leads to interpretative issues for $\exp(-ipx)$ because $-p$ moves to the left while uses a forward moving scheme. In electromagnetic reflection, however, one has the same scenario and so we argue that at each point x , there exists an $a(p)\exp(ipx)$ free particle ensemble (distribution) moving to the right, but also a corresponding reflected set of probability waves $a(-p)\exp(-ipx)$. If $a(p)=a(-p)$, the reflection occurs without an extra phase whereas if $a(p)=-a(-p)$, it receives a shift of 3.14 .